

**Examination of Self-Confidence and Self-Esteem Values in
the Project Empowering Girls through Sports, organized
by the Turkish National Olympic Committee in
Diyarbakir for Girls Aged 10-14**

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ABSTRACT

There will be an explanation provided in this research as to whether or not there is a difference between the levels of self-confidence and self-esteem of girls who are socioeconomically disadvantaged and who participate in the Basketball, Volleyball, and Badminton sports course that is held in Diyarbakir by the Turkish National Olympic Committee. The participants in this course range in age from 10 to 14 years at the time. In teenagers, it is generally acknowledged

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that low self-esteem and a lack of self-confidence are recognized as significant risk factors. The link between self-confidence and the construction of a healthy lifestyle in their future lives will be described, and it will be revealed that sports will add to the literature by demonstrating the relationship between the two.

The relational survey model, which is one of the main survey models, will be used in this study and investigation. The purpose of this study is to investigate the link between the values of self-esteem and self-confidence and the girls between the ages of 10 and 14 who participated in the weekend sports course that was arranged by the National Olympic Committee of Turkey. Girls who are between the ages of 10 and 14 and who are currently enrolled in the 2021-2022 academic year and who reside in Diyarbakır are the subjects of this research.

Key Words: *Daughters, Basketball, Self-Respect*

INTRODUCTION

Girls who have completed their secondary education and are now entering their teenage years' experience a number of adjustments. These factors include those that are cognitive, physical, and psychological. In particular during these times, it is of the utmost importance to find a way to positively overcome the psychosocial development process via the medium of sports. Some research on self-confidence and self-esteem are included in the review of the relevant literature; nevertheless, it seems that these studies are insufficient. It is believed that this study will be significant in order to provide additional sources of information that will be of assistance to the free sports schools and other initiatives of this kind that are carried out annually by the Turkish National Olympic Committee. Furthermore, it is believed that the psychological and social influence of school sports and sports courses on females will contribute to the Ministry of National Education, the Ministry of Youth and Sports, and the area of sports sciences. This is because of the fact that girls are more likely to participate in sports and sports courses.

Since many years ago, people in our nation and all over the globe have been discussing the impact that participating in sports while attending school has on the growth and development of individuals. Numerous studies have been conducted to investigate the impact that participating in sports has on a person's development, particularly during the developmental stage that we refer to as adolescence. On the other hand, when these research are analyzed, it is

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believed that there are not enough studies on the involvement of females in sports. In this regard, the topic of this study may be characterized as an investigation of the impact that the involvement of teenage females in school sports teams or their lack of engagement in sports has on their levels of self-confidence and self-esteem values.

An individual's interests, attitudes, talents, skills, way of speaking, looks, and style of adapting are all components that make up their personality. Personality is the phrase that encompasses all of these aspects. Self is the term used to describe the value assessment that a person makes about themselves. Motivating oneself to do action in order to accomplish a goal or to have pleasure in one's life is the opposite of motivation. In the event that such a desire has not yet reached a level that is capable of motivating the person, this indicates that their degree of motivation is insufficient. Heredity and environment work together to produce development, which is the result of this interplay. The process of development is both slow and ongoing 1. It is possible to describe the five fundamental ideas that are associated with development as follows: development is a dynamic phenomenon that is the product of genetic uniqueness; development is a process of growing specialization; development is an ordered process, and there is a balance in development 2; and development is a process that occurs over time. Since ancient times, competitive physical activities have been a significant measure of strength for communities. The people and governments have shown a great deal of interest in all athletic competitions, which have grown more popular. The notion of today's contemporary sport, which was conveyed with the names "Gymnastics" and "Agonistic" in ancient times, was developed from the Latin word *Disportare* in the 17th century. This notion has been able to be described in a much larger perspective in light of physiological, social, and psychological assessments, particularly in the past century, as a result of the interaction of the concept of sport with other scientific disciplines. Sport is the reality that is expressed in the concept of sport from a philosophical standpoint. In terms of sociology, sports reinterpret the spirit, main subject, and essence of sports with each added information compiled from its philosophies. Additionally, sports investigate the effects of sports on human behavior and relations with the environment by making connections in light of various theories and other branches of science.

Individuals have their own unique ways of seeing themselves, the world, other people, and the environment around them. The explanation provided by Kağıtçıbaşı included the third self-structure, as well as the heterogeneous self and associated self-conceptions, which are included in the category of self-kinds. A self-structure that encompasses both autonomy and relational

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inclinations is noticed in families in developed metropolitan regions of countries with collectivist traditions, as stated by Kağıtçıbaşı¹. This self-structure is exhibited in families where emotional links between generations do not dissolve, but material linkages weaken. In this context, self-determination and active participation might be seen as autonomy 3.

In terms of children's socialization and the development of their sense of self, the contributions of both the family and the school are quite significant. The parents, on the other hand, are entitled to the most sizable portion. In a world that is replete with visual stimuli, life and learning have not stopped. According to Getman, "Vision and intelligence are very closely related. The child can know what he sees and understands; this determines his cultural intelligence." Hearing is the most crucial factor in the process of learning a language and developing interpersonal interactions.

The natural and logical ramifications of Adler's approach led to principles of behavior modification. These principles are made possible by taking into consideration the emotional needs of children. The fifth premise of behavior modification is to have communication skills, mischief aims, logical and natural consequences, and mischief goals. Participation in sporting activities has been shown to have good benefits on a healthy lifestyle, which is a fact that is well acknowledged. Taking this into consideration, it is essential for every single person who constitutes the society to take part in sporting activities in order to promote the development of generations that are healthy. In light of the fact that development varies from one time to the next and that the distinctive developmental features of each period are taken into consideration, it is essential to study activities that will have a good impact on this process. Taking this into consideration, conducting research into the impacts of sporting activities on individuals of different ages will have an impact on the development of the process of emotional discipline.

Sport is a pedagogical, biological, and wide notion that improves a person's natural (organic) mental health, controls social interactions, and takes it to a specific level in terms of mental and movement. This is the concept that is being discussed here. The Latin phrase "I Disport" is the literal translation of the word "sport," and "Delsport" is a shortened version of the words. Playing is a method to kill time and take a break from professional responsibilities. A collection of activities that individuals engage in to make use of their physical, mental, and emotional capabilities in a domain that they are interested in is referred to as sports. These activities are instructional, instructive, competitive, and entertaining. The term "sport" refers to any and all activities that are performed with the purpose of engaging in physical relaxation, having fun,

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and spending time in a happy and pleasant manner. As time goes on, technological advancements continue to come along. They are bodily movements that are done within the framework of specific regulations in all civilizations for the aim of competition and victory, as well as the endeavor to triumph over others. Because living standards are always changing, these motions are performed. The sphere of sports has also been a significant economic sector in our day, one that has captured the attention of everyone and appealed to them even if they did not want to participate in it. Movement is the most fundamental meaning of the term "sport." An individual may participate in sports, which include a social framework, as well as participate in sports in groups. The idea of self-confidence has been defined in a variety of diverse ways, and these meanings have been determined via the examination of the literature.

Self-confidence is one of the principles that contribute to the formation of personality, according to Kugle (1983) 6. In other words, it is a phenomena that is experienced by an individual as a consequence of their own self-evaluation. Self-confidence is defined by Feltz (1988) as "the belief that an individual will successfully perform a specific activity rather than a general characteristic." He provided an illustration to illustrate this definition by referencing the following scenario: a person may have an elevated level of self-confidence when it comes to playing golf, but they may have a low level of self-confidence in general. Consequently, Feltz shifted his level of self-confidence from a general to a particular one. According to Bandura (1997) 8, the idea of self-confidence refers to an individual's perception of how valued they believe they are. In order to have moments that are pleasant, rewarding, meaningful, loving, and balanced, it is fundamentally necessary to have self-confidence. In an effective way, this criterion is affected by any effort that is made to boost one's self-confidence.

A list of things that you have done and of which you are proud will serve as a guide for you. Identify characteristics that are liked and appreciated by other people. A person who has poor self-esteem tends to concentrate on the bad elements of themselves rather than the good ones. It is a source of comfort to accept who we are, including both the good and bad aspects of our personalities. This brings us to the following phase, which is to determine what aspects of your negativity, or characteristics are considered to be negative. Possibly, we have some deficiencies. In spite of this, it is always conceivable for these deficiencies to undergo a transformation. Increasing your self-confidence may be accomplished by making goals for the future and working to alter negative thoughts and feelings of inadequacy.

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It has been suggested by Karamoy et al. (2018) 10 that self-confidence plays a significant role in human existence and acts as a motivating factor for individuals to act in the manner that they want. In this manner, those who possess an elevated level of self-confidence are able to control the outcomes of their life. According to Akagunduz (2006) 11, self-confidence is defined as the condition of being in harmony with one's surroundings or with oneself as a consequence of generating good attitudes about oneself. 'The sensation of being liked' and 'the feeling of being competent' are the two fundamental aspects of self-confidence, as stated by Humphreys (2000), who states that self-confidence falls into two categories. In order to illustrate these ideas, he provides the following illustration: If a kid who is attending school is timid, shy, excessively silent, aggressive, or bullying, then these characteristics indicate that there are concerns with the child's likeability.

If the youngster is scared to take on a new project, is terrified of failing, and feels dejected every time he makes a mistake, these symptoms also suggest that the child doubts his ability to do the task at hand.

Individuals who possess a high level of self-confidence are those who are able to acknowledge the circumstances that they are unable to alter, possess the bravery to alter the circumstances that they are able to alter, and possess the discernment to differentiate between the circumstances that they are able to alter and those that they are unable to alter. His calm and joyful demeanor brings joy to everyone who are in his immediate vicinity. Those who have low self-esteem need the acceptance and admiration of others in order to have a sense of accomplishment. The individual is unable to handle criticism, avoids conflict, and is afraid of failing. Self-esteem is one of the most significant elements that contribute to the development of an individual's personality, and it has the ability to influence and guide an individual throughout their whole life. Self-esteem, which plays a key role in the formation of an individual's personality and has an impact on the individual's perceptions and emotional thoughts as a whole, is a vital contributor to the individual's socialization. The number of research that have been conducted on self-concept, which is considered to be one of the most significant aspects of personality, has significantly expanded in recent years. In addition, it is believed that the rise in the emphasis that contemporary individuals place on the idea of "self" and the rise in the degree to which societies are becoming more individualistic are both factors that contribute to these circumstances. Individuals' conceptions of themselves and their beliefs

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about who and what they are, also known as their identities, are referred to as their self-concepts, as stated by Yavuzer (2002).

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In terms of children's socialization and the development of their sense of self, the contributions of both the family and the school are quite significant. The parents, on the other hand, are entitled to the most sizable portion. In a world that is replete with visual stimuli, life and learning have not stopped. According to Getman, "Vision and intelligence are very closely related. The child can know what he sees and understands; this determines his cultural intelligence." Hearing is the most important aspect of learning a language and developing interactions with other people.

The natural and logical ramifications of Adler's approach led to principles of behavior modification. These principles are made possible by taking into consideration the emotional needs of children. Skills in communication, aims of mischief, logical and natural consequences, and principles of behavior modification number 18. In addition to the views that individuals have about themselves, those who play a significant part in the lives of other people (parents, siblings, instructors, friends, and so on) are also influenced by the thoughts and actions that they have toward the person throughout the process of establishing the self-concept. Self-esteem, according to his definition, is an individual's judgment of their own self-concept, as well as their like, approval, and total contentment with the result.

In his work published in 1986, Yorukoğlu (19) provided a definition of self-concept, which he described as the individual's perception and comprehension of his or her own self. Another definition of the self-concept describes it as the individual's vision of himself, which includes his own attitudes, emotions, perceptions, values, and behaviors²⁰. This is an example of how the self-concept should be understood.

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It is possible to say that the person who responds to the question "Who am I?" develops favorable judgments about his physical appearance, personality, and character, as well as his ethical principles and morals, social benefit, and psychologically harmonious personality, together with a feeling of ability and integrated confidence.

The phenomena of self-love that is formed from the self-concept that a person achieves as a result of coming to terms with themselves is known as self-esteem. There are five components that make up self-esteem: cognitive, emotional, physical, and social. There are a number of factors that contribute to the formation and growth of self-esteem, including the experience of being valued and content, the demonstration of abilities, skills, and knowledge, acceptance, success, and the feeling of being liked, loved, and respected.

The most significant element that has an impact on our personalities is in fact ourselves. A person's self is comprised of their views on their own personality and their own way of seeing the world. When seen from this angle, the concept of self may likewise be understood as a distinct facet of personality 21.

Individuals' existing personal capabilities, qualities, goals, ideals, and expectations for the future are all included inside the self, which is an expression of these things. An individual's self-concept may be defined as their knowledge of their own identities 22. As a consequence of this, the idea of the self may be understood to include the emotions, assessments, and perceptions that people have of their own internal state of affairs. There is a direct correlation between low self-esteem and deficient performance. Having the sense of accomplishment and being praised is of utmost significance in this setting. In the event that a youngster does well, he is aware that he has performed well and perceives himself to be valued because of this. Individuals are driven to safeguard their self-confidence, self-image, and image of themselves. In most cases, individuals are impacted by the beliefs and actions of the group to which they belong as well as by the actions of other individuals²⁴. Adolescence and beyond are crucial periods for the development of human political identities. According to the idea, which shifts depending on the circumstances and is impacted by history, identity has been formed in accordance with the environment throughout the course of the last twenty years.

Depending on the distribution, one may conclude which one is more significant. People, regardless of their age, whether they are students or teachers, get to decide what sets them apart from others.

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One further way to think about self-concept is as a pattern that an individual creates for himself or herself in his or her inner world. This pattern has a significant impact on the individual's personality and later years. The individual's self-confidence and the development of an introvert or extrovert personality characteristics are both impacted as a result. The formation of the self is influenced by a variety of social, mental, and physical experiences.

No human being is born into this world with a sense of who they are as an individual. When it comes to the formation of an individual's self-concept, the social environment, which includes the individual's mother, father, siblings, and friends, plays a significant impact. This social context is the source of the individual's learning and development of his or her self-concept. This procedure starts with the person coming into being, which is the 26th step.

The evaluation and perception of oneself by a person is what constitutes their self-concept. In this context, the experiences and cognitive structure of the person are incredibly significant 27. It is possible for a person to identify good aspects of themselves and love themselves even as they are criticizing themselves. Because of a person's self-esteem and the respect they have for their personality, their exceptional characteristics are brought to the forefront. mostly due to the fact that self-esteem is the condition of being self-assured and content without having any perceptions of one's own superiority or inferiority. One's self-esteem may be thought of as the psychological or emotional aspect of oneself. Not only does a person possess certain knowledge about themselves, but they also have specific sentiments inside themselves about who they are. Self-esteem is a measurement of self-love and emotion; thus it is a measure of both.

According to Plummer (2011) 28, the development of good self-esteem in people is dependent on seven fundamental components. What are these components? He came to the conclusion that "Self-Knowledge" was the first of these fundamental components. According to him, the growth of an individual's self-esteem is based on a number of fundamental principles, including the individual's self-perception, the ability to identify their own features, and the individual's knowledge of their own personal histories. "It and Others" was the term he gave to the second item, and he discussed the significance of persons being able to recognize their own emotions and ideas as well as those of others, as well as the ability to communicate those feelings and thoughts in a manner that is acceptable and suitable, in order to cultivate a healthy sense of self-esteem. In the third item, which was presented under the heading "Self-Acceptance," it was mentioned that the self-esteem of people is a result of their awareness of the significance of embracing their distinctive traits and distinctions.

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Different self-concepts are shown by a person's self-esteem when they portray themselves to others. It is possible for a person to think of themselves as a competent football player and to have an interest in educational studies.

The individual's personality is a phenomena that may be characterized by these traits. A realistic and objective appraisal of the perspectives of actual and non-existent talents, abilities, and qualities is what we mean when we talk about self-respect. Self-respect encompasses all of the information that is included inside the phenomena of the self. The intended level of self-esteem will manifest itself if there is a proportion or harmony between the self that is recognized and the self that is meant to exist.

"Personal Competence" is the title of the fourth article that is presented here. In this section, he discussed the significance of being able to identify the challenges that life presents and the value of conquering these challenges by having an understanding of the personal qualities of those who are facing these challenges. The "Self-Expression" category is the sixth item on the list. One of the things that was brought up was the significance of persons being able to appropriately articulate themselves in order to cultivate their sense of self-confidence. The sixth item is titled "Being Self-Confident," and it sheds light on the influence that an individual's level of self-confidence has on their capacity to make decisions, choose various courses of action, and effectively deal with challenges as a direct consequence of this confidence. "Self-Awareness" is the seventh and last thing, and it is defined as the title of the last item. On the subject of the growth of self-esteem, it was said that the influence of people's self-awareness, their capacity to deal with negative emotions, and their willingness to be open to changes that may occur to them are all factors that play a role.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The relational scanning model, which is one of the main scanning models of quantitative research methodologies, will be used in this investigation on the part of the researcher.

Research Model

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A screening method called the relational screening model looks for covariation between two or more variables. According to the universal screening model, in a universe with a high number of elements, a general assessment of the universe is made by scanning the whole universe or a subset of samples. Whether the variables change simultaneously or not, the relational screening model tries to figure out why the shift occurred 29. This study aims to investigate the correlation between the self-esteem and self-confidence levels of girls aged 10-14 and their involvement in the weekend sports program offered by the Turkish National Olympic Committee. The following are regarded as the research's limitations:

1. The study will only focus on a few schools in the province of Diyarbakır's Bağlar area.
2. Will be restricted to the responses from the Self-Esteem and Self-Efficacy Scale (KSÖS), which is a two-dimensional measure of self-esteem; Doğan (2011) 30 converted the scale to Turkish; and Akın (2007) produced the Self-Confidence Scale. ³¹.

Population and Sample

The research's population comprises females in the Diyarbakır province between the ages of 10 and 14, who are enrolled in the 2021–2022 academic year. The study sample consists of 300 girls aged 10-14 who will participate in a sports course in volleyball, basketball, and badminton offered by the Turkish National Olympic Committee in the Bağlar District of Diyarbakır Province during the 2021–2022 academic year. The study will take place at six secondary schools in the Bağlar district: Nuri Zekiye Has Secondary School, Eczacılar Secondary School, 700.Yıl Secondary School, Koşu Yolu Secondary School, Kazım Karabekir Secondary School, and Mevlana Halit Secondary School.

Because of this, the selection of schools was made using a straightforward random sample technique. All elements in a defined universe have an independent and equal chance of being selected into the sample using the sample selection technique known as simple random sampling. Each element has the same probability of being selected for sampling, and the selection of one element has no bearing on the selection of another.

Data Collection Tools:

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To gather information for the study, the investigator divided the task into three sections:

1: Form for Personal Information The researcher will create a personal information form with questions on the pupils' age, grade level, history of participation in sports, and household income level.

2: Scale of Self-Confidence The study used the Self-Confidence Scale, which was created by Akin (2007) 31 to gauge each person's current level of self-confidence. The rating system will be a 5-point Likert type (1: Never, 2: Sometimes, 3: Often, 4: Usually, 5: Always).

3: Tafarodi and Swann (2001) 32 created the 16-item, self-report Two-Dimensional Self-Esteem Scale (Self-Like and Self-Efficacy Scale, KSES). The "self-love" and "self-efficacy" aspects of the scale are used to assess self-esteem. It is rated on a 5-point Likert scale. Doğan created the Turkish translation of KSÖÖ (2011).³⁰.

Analysis of Data

The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) 24.0 package application will be utilized for statistical analysis in the evaluation of the study's results. The distribution of the data will be ascertained by the use of the Shapiro-Wilk and Anderson-Darling tests, which are normality tests, and the link between the students' levels of self-esteem and confidence will be ascertained through the use of the Spearman's rho correlation test.

RESULTS

Table 1 provides details regarding the age, social class, and family income of the female teenagers who took part in the study and who play sports or do not play sports.

Table 1. Socio-demographic characteristics

		<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%
<u>Yas</u>	12	57	%48,3	37	%38,9
	13	39	%33,1	52	%54,7
	14	22	%18,6	6	%6,3
<u>Sınıf</u>	7	60	%50,8	38	%40,0
	8	58	%49,2	57	%60,0
	Alt	4	%3,4	0	%0,0
<u>Aile Gelir Seviyesi</u>	Orta	103	%87,3	85	%89,5
	Üst	11	%9,3	10	%10,5

The ages of the female adolescents who do not participate in athletics are as follows: of those who do, 57 (48.3%) are 12 years old, 39 (33.1%) are 13 years old, and 22 (18.6%) are 14 years old; of those who do, 37 (38.9%) were 12 years old, and 52 (54.7%) of them, 13.6 (6.3%) were 14 years old. Of the females who do not play sports, 60 (50.8%) had grade levels of 7, 58 (49.2%) had grade levels of 8, and 7 (60.0%) of the 38 (40.0%) female adolescents who play sports are in the eighth grade. It can be shown that 85 (89.5%) of the female adolescents who participate in sports are at a medium socioeconomic level when taking into account the family income levels of the teenage females who do not participate in sports: 4 (3.4%) are low, 103 (87.3%) are medium, and 11 (9.3%) are high. Ten (9.5%) fall within the high socioeconomic category in terms of economic status.

Table 2 provides details on the amount of time female teenagers included in the study spent doing sports.

Table 2. Duration of Exercise (Year)

	<i>N</i>	$\bar{X}$	<i>Ss</i>	<i>Min.</i>	<i>Max.</i>
Spor Yapma Süresi (yıl)	95	3,87	1,57	1	8

It was revealed that female adolescents who participated in athletics for a length of (3.87 ± 1.57) years. Details on the Sports Played by Female Adolescents Table 3 provides information on the sports played by the female adolescents taking part in the study.

Table 3. Branch Type

		<i>n</i>	%
<u>Basketbol</u>	<u>Oynayan</u>	22	23,2
	<u>Oynamayan</u>	73	76,8
	<u>Toplam</u>	95	100,0
<u>Voleybol</u>	<u>Oynayan</u>	39	41,1
	<u>Oynamayan</u>	56	58,9
	<u>Toplam</u>	95	100,0
<u>Futbol</u>	<u>Oynayan</u>	4	4,2
	<u>Oynamayan</u>	91	95,8
	<u>Toplam</u>	95	100,0
<u>Hentbol</u>	<u>Oynayan</u>	11	11,6
	<u>Oynamayan</u>	84	88,4
	<u>Toplam</u>	95	100,0
<u>Masa Tenisi</u>	<u>Oynayan</u>	10	10,5
	<u>Oynamayan</u>	85	89,5
	<u>Toplam</u>	95	100,0
<u>Futsal</u>	<u>Oynayan</u>	2	2,1
	<u>Oynamayan</u>	93	97,9
	<u>Toplam</u>	95	100,0
<u>Atletizm</u>	<u>Oynayan</u>	9	9,5
	<u>Oynamayan</u>	86	90,5

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The basketball variable shows that 73 (76.8%) of female teenagers do not play, whereas 22 (23.2%) do. The volleyball variable shows that 39 (41.1%) of the female teenagers are players, while 56 (58.9%) are not. The football variable shows that 91 (95.8%) of female adolescents do not play, whereas 4 (4.2%) of them do. The handball variable shows that 84 (88.4%) female teenagers do not play, whereas 11 (11.6%) participate. The table tennis variable shows that 85 (89.5%) of the female teenagers do not play, whereas 10 (10.1%) of them do. The futsal variable shows that females are divided between 2 (2.1%) who play and 93 (97.9%) who don't. Nineteen (9.5%) female teenagers participate in sports, whereas eighty-six (90.5%) do not. As per the Taekwondo variable, out of the females, 2 (2.1%) play while 93 (97.9%) do not participate.

Figure 1. Branch Type

Table 4 provides information on the levels of self-confidence and self-esteem among female teenagers who take part in the study and who play sports or not.

Table 4. Differences in the Self-Esteem and Self-Confidence of Female Adolescents Whether They Participate in Sports or Not

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		$\bar{X}$	Ss	t	p
<u>Benlik Saygısı</u>	<u>Spor Yapmayan</u>	74,848	17,092	-1,338	0,182
	<u>Spor Yapan</u>	77,979	16,828		
<u>İç Özgüven</u>	<u>Spor Yapmayan</u>	62,593	10,220	-3,229	0,001
	<u>Spor Yapan</u>	66,663	7,593		
<u>Dış Özgüven</u>	<u>Spor Yapmayan</u>	62,644	10,497	-3,903	0,000
	<u>Spor Yapan</u>	67,526	6,905		
<u>Özgüven Toplam</u>	<u>Spor Yapmayan</u>	128,907	20,557	-3,749	0,000
	<u>Spor Yapan</u>	138,158	13,898		

The difference between the group averages was not determined to be statistically significant ($p>0.05$) based on the results of the t test, which was used to evaluate whether the self-esteem averages of female teenagers varied substantially according to the sport variable. The t test, which was performed to ascertain if there was a significant difference in the average self-confidence of female teenagers based on the sport variable, revealed that there was a statistically significant difference between the group averages ($t=-3.229$; $p<0.05$). It was shown that girls who participate in sports had better internal self-confidence ratings (66.663) than girls who do not participate in sports (62.593).

The statistical significance of the difference between the group averages was determined by conducting a t test to see if the average external self-confidence of female adolescents varied substantially based on the sport variable ($t=-3.903$; $p<0.05$).

Girls who participate in sports had higher exterior self-confidence ratings (67.526) than girls who do not participate in sports (62.644). The difference between the group averages was determined to be statistically significant ($t=-3.749$; $p<0.05$) based on the results of the t test, which was used to assess whether the overall self-confidence averages of female adolescents varied substantially according to the sport variable. It was shown that females who participate in sports had higher overall self-confidence ratings (138.158) than girls who do not participate in sports (128.907).

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Table 5 presents the results of a Pearson Correlation Analysis examining the link between the levels of self-esteem and confidence in female teenagers who engage in the study and who play sports and those who do not.

Table 5. The relationship between the self-esteem and self-confidence levels of female adolescents who play sports and those who do not is examined using Pearson correlation analysis.

		Spor Yapmayan			Spor Yapan		
		n	R	p	n	r	p
<u>İç özgüven</u>	<u>Benlik saygısı</u>	118	0,496	0,000	95	0,567	0,000
<u>Dış özgüven</u>	<u>Benlik saygısı</u>	118	0,526	0,000	95	0,481	0,000
<u>Özgüven toplam</u>	<u>Benlik saygısı</u>	118	0,535	0,000	95	0,558	0,000

At the 49.6% level, a positive and substantial link was discovered between self-confidence and self-esteem in female teenagers who do not participate in sports. ($p < 0.05$; $r = 0.496$). As a result, the self-esteem score rises in tandem with the internal self-confidence score. At the level of 52.6%, a positive and substantial link was discovered between external self-confidence and self-esteem. ($p < 0.05$; $r = 0.526$). Consequently, the self-esteem score rises in tandem with the exterior self-confidence score. At the 53.5% level, a strong and positive correlation was discovered between overall self-confidence and self-esteem. ($p < 0.05$; $r = 0.535$). As a result, the self-confidence score rises along with the overall self-confidence score.

At the 56.7% level, a favorable and substantial association between self-esteem and self-confidence was discovered in girls and adolescents who participate in sports. ($p < 0.05$; $r = 0.567$). As a result, the self-confidence score rises along with the self-confidence score.

At the 48.1% level, a substantial positive association was discovered between external self-confidence and self-esteem. ($p < 0.05$; $r = 0.481$). Consequently, the self-esteem score rises in

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tandem with the exterior self-confidence score. At the 55.8% level, a positive and substantial association was discovered between overall self-confidence and self-esteem. ($p < 0.05$; $r = 0.558$). As a result, the self-confidence score rises along with the overall self-confidence score.

Table 6 provides information on the comparison of family income levels with the levels of self-confidence and self-esteem among female teenagers who play sports and are study participants.

Table 6. Self-Confidence and Self-Esteem of Female Adolescents Playing Sports at Various Income Levels

		<i>N</i>	$\bar{X}$	<i>Ss</i>	<i>MW</i>	<i>p</i>
<u>Benlik Saygısı</u>	Orta	85	77,694	16,680	375,000	0,542
	Üst	10	80,400	18,804		
<u>İç Özgüven</u>	Orta	85	66,588	7,677	405,500	0,813
	Üst	10	67,300	7,181		
<u>Dış Özgüven</u>	Orta	85	67,424	6,781	379,000	0,576
	Üst	10	68,400	8,235		
<u>Özgüven Toplam</u>	Orta	85	137,988	13,871	397,500	0,739
	Üst	10	139,600	14,796		

Results of the non-parametric Mann Whitney-U test were used to assess whether there was a significant difference according to the family income level variable in the overall score averages of female adolescents' self-esteem, internal self-confidence, external self-confidence, and self-confidence. The higher income groups' distributions weren't typical. There was no statistically significant change ($p > 0.05$).

Table 7 provides information on the self-esteem and confidence levels of female teenagers who play sports and are included in the study.

Table 7. Self-Confidence and Self-Esteem of Female Adolescents Participating in Sports from Various Classes

	<i>Sınıf</i>	<i>N</i>	$\bar{X}$	<i>Ss</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
<u>Benlik Saygısı</u>	7	38	81,053	16,886	1,462	0,147
	8	57	75,930	16,622		
<u>İç Özgüven</u>	7	38	67,816	8,285	1,211	0,229
	8	57	65,895	7,065		
<u>Dış Özgüven</u>	7	38	68,184	7,533	0,757	0,451
	8	57	67,088	6,484		
<u>Özgüven Toplam</u>	7	38	140,105	15,514	1,117	0,267
	8	57	136,860	12,685		

The difference between the group mean scores was not found to be statistically significant ($p>0.05$) as a result of the t-test that was used to determine whether or not female adolescents' self-esteem, internal self-confidence, external self-confidence, and self-confidence mean scores differ significantly according to the class variable.

Table 8 provides information on assessing the levels of self-confidence and self-esteem among female teenagers who are included in the study and who play sports according to their age groups.

Table 8. Self-Confidence and Self-Esteem of Female Adolescents Playing Sports at Various Ages

		<i>N</i>	$\bar{X}$	<i>Ss</i>	<i>KW</i>	<i>p</i>
<u>Benlik Saygısı</u>	12	37	80,649	16,932	2,402	0,301
	13	52	76,462	16,285		
	14	6	74,667	21,565		
<u>İç Özgüven</u>	12	37	67,811	8,399	4,141	0,126
	13	52	66,212	7,094		
	14	6	63,500	6,221		
<u>Dış Özgüven</u>	12	37	68,162	7,636	0,588	0,745
	13	52	67,250	6,343		
	14	6	66,000	7,720		
<u>Özgüven Toplam</u>	12	37	140,108	15,728	2,574	0,276
	13	52	137,308	12,574		
	14	6	133,500	13,263		

Since the frequency distributions in the groups in the age variable were not normal, the non-parametric Kruskal Wallis H-Test was used to determine whether the mean total scores of female adolescents for self-esteem, internal self-confidence, external self-confidence, and self-confidence showed a significant difference in terms of age variable. The difference between the group mean scores was not found to be significant ($p > 0.05$).

Table 9 provides information on the assessment of the self-worth and self-assurance of female teenagers who took part in the study and who played basketball and did not.

Table 9. Self-Confidence and Self-Esteem of Female Adolescent Basketball Players and Non-Players

		<i>N</i>	$\bar{X}$	<i>Ss</i>	<i>MW</i>	<i>p</i>
<u>Benlik Saygısı</u>	<u>Yapan</u>	22	77,818	17,533	796,000	0,950
	<u>Yapmayan</u>	73	78,027	16,735		
<u>İç Özgüven</u>	<u>Yapan</u>	22	65,636	6,666	677,500	0,268
	<u>Yapmayan</u>	73	66,973	7,867		
<u>Dış Özgüven</u>	<u>Yapan</u>	22	66,591	8,600	752,500	0,655
	<u>Yapmayan</u>	73	67,808	6,350		
<u>Özgüven Toplam</u>	<u>Yapan</u>	22	136,091	14,468	708,500	0,404
	<u>Yapmayan</u>	73	138,781	13,763		

To ascertain whether there is a significant difference in the self-esteem, internal self-confidence, external self-confidence, and self-confidence mean scores of female adolescents based on the basketball variable, the non-parametric Mann Whitney-U test resulted in a non-statistically significant difference between the group mean scores. It had significance. ($p > 0.05$).

Table 10 provides information on the self-esteem and confidence levels of female teenagers who played volleyball and did not engage in the study.

Table 10. Self-Confidence and Self-Esteem of Female Adolescent Volleyball Players and Non-Players

	<i>Voleybol</i>	<i>N</i>	$\bar{X}$	<i>Ss</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
Benlik Saygısı	Yapan	39	86,564	10,838	4,567	0,000
	Yapmayan	56	72,000	17,725		
İç Özgüven	Yapan	39	70,282	5,689	4,207	0,000
	Yapmayan	56	64,143	7,773		
Dış Özgüven	Yapan	39	70,256	5,072	3,391	0,001
	Yapmayan	56	65,625	7,399		
Özgüven Toplam	Yapan	39	144,615	10,353	4,082	0,000
	Yapmayan	56	133,661	14,349		

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The statistical significance of the difference between the group averages was determined by conducting a t test to see if the average self-esteem ratings of female teenagers showed a significant difference based on the volleyball variable ($t=4.567$; $p<0.05$). It was shown that females who participate in volleyball sports had higher average self-esteem (86.564) than girls who do not (72.000).

The statistical significance of the difference between the group averages was determined by conducting a t test to see if the average self-confidence scores of female teenagers showed a significant difference based on the volleyball variable ($t=4.207$; $p<0.05$). Girls who played volleyball had a mean internal self-confidence score of 70.282, which was higher than the mean internal self-confidence score of 64.143 for those who did not play volleyball.

The statistical significance of the difference between the group averages was determined by conducting a t test to see if the average external self-confidence ratings of female teenagers showed a significant difference based on the volleyball variable ($t=3.391$; $p<0.05$). Girls who play volleyball have an average external self-confidence score of 70.256, which is higher than the mean score of girls who don't play volleyball (65.625).

The difference between the group average scores was determined to be statistically significant ($t=4.082$; $p<0.05$) based on the results of the t test, which was performed to ascertain if the average overall self-confidence scores of the females exhibited a significant difference according to the volleyball variable. It was discovered that the average total score of girls who play volleyball (144.615) is higher than the average total score of girls who do not play volleyball (133.661).

Table 11 provides information on the study of the self-confidence and self-esteem levels of female teenagers who played handball and did not engage in the research.

Table 11. Female Adolescents' Levels of Self-Esteem and Self-Confidence in Relation to Handball Sports Participation

	Hentbol	N	$\bar{X}$	<u>Ss</u>	MW	<u>p</u>
Benlik Saygısı	Yapan	11	61,091	18,684	200,500	0,002
	Yapmayan	84	80,191	15,360		
İç Özgüven	Yapan	11	63,273	7,734	315,500	0,088
	Yapmayan	84	67,107	7,507		
Dış Özgüven	Yapan	11	65,000	7,029	358,000	0,226
	Yapmayan	84	67,857	6,862		
Özgüven Toplam	Yapan	11	132,091	14,117	327,000	0,116
	Yapmayan	84	138,952	13,756		

The difference between the group averages was found to be statistically significant (Mann Whitney U = 200.500) as a result of the non-parametric Mann Whitney-U test, which was carried out to ascertain whether the average self-esteem scores of female adolescents showed a significant difference according to the handball variable. $p < 0.05$).

It was discovered that the mean score for self-esteem among girls who do not participate in handball sports (61.091) was lower than the mean score for girls who do not participate in handball sports (80.191).

The difference between the group averages was not found to be statistically significant ($p > 0.05$) as a result of the Mann Whitney-U test, which was carried out to determine whether the mean scores of female adolescents' internal, external, and total self-confidence showed a significant difference according to the handball variable.

Table 12 provides information on the assessment of the self-worth and self-assurance levels of female teenagers who took part in the study and played table tennis and did not.

Table 12. Self-Confidence and Self-Esteem of Female Adolescents Playing and Not Playing Handball

		<i>N</i>	$\bar{X}$	<i>Ss</i>	<i>MW</i>	<i>p</i>
Benlik Saygısı	Yapan	10	72,400	17,834	326,500	0,230
	Yapmayan	85	78,635	16,694		
İç Özgüven	Yapan	10	59,300	10,563	225,500	0,015
	Yapmayan	85	67,529	6,734		
Dış Özgüven	Yapan	10	64,500	7,276	297,500	0,121
	Yapmayan	85	67,882	6,816		
Özgüven Toplam	Yapan	10	127,500	17,232	244,500	0,029
	Yapmayan	85	139,412	13,009		

The non-parametric Mann Whitney-U test, which was used to assess whether the internal self-confidence score averages of the participant groups that played table tennis and those who did not, were normal because the frequency distributions were not normal, according to the table tennis variable (Mann Whitney U) of female adolescents, revealed a statistically significant difference between the group averages. (=225,500; $p < 0.05$) showed that a significant change was detected.

It was discovered that the mean internal self-confidence score of females who play table tennis (59.300) is lower than the mean score of girls who do not play (67.529).

The Mann Whitney-U test was used to see if there was a statistically significant difference in the girls' average total self-confidence scores based on the table tennis variable. The results showed that there was a statistically significant difference between the group average scores (Mann Whitney U=244.500; $p < 0.05$).

It was discovered that the average overall self-confidence score of female teenagers who play table tennis (127.500) is lower than the average total self-confidence score of females who do not play the sport (139.412).

The difference in the group mean scores was not found to be statistically significant ($p > 0.05$) based on the Mann Whitney-U test, which was used to evaluate whether the mean scores of female adolescents' external self-confidence and self-esteem showed a significant difference based on the table tennis variable.

Table 13 provides information on the assessment of the self-worth and self-assurance of female teenagers who took part in the study and who played sports or not.

Table 13. Self-Confidence and Self-Esteem of Female Adolescents Playing and Not Playing Handball

		<i>N</i>	$\bar{X}$	<i>Ss</i>	<i>MW</i>	<i>p</i>
Benlik Saygısı	Yapan	9	71,556	12,561	244,000	0,068
	Yapmayan	86	78,651	17,132		
İç Özgüven	Yapan	9	66,333	6,500	365,000	0,780
	Yapmayan	86	66,698	7,731		
Dış Özgüven	Yapan	9	67,333	6,245	379,500	0,924
	Yapmayan	86	67,547	7,004		
Özgüven Toplam	Yapan	9	137,889	12,494	385,500	0,985
	Yapmayan	86	138,186	14,103		

The non-parametric Mann Whitney-U test was used to find the difference between the group score averages in order to assess whether the self-esteem, internal self-confidence, external self-confidence, and self-confidence average scores of female adolescents demonstrated significant differences based on the athletics variable. The non-parametric Mann Whitney-U test revealed that the difference was not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$).

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The purpose of this study was to investigate the association between the levels of self-esteem and confidence in secondary school teenage females aged 10-14 and their participation in school sports teams. The following order of interpretation was applied to the research's conclusions.

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There was no discernible relationship between the self-esteem levels of the 213 female adolescents in the research, who were between the ages of 10 and 14, and whether or not they were involved in sports.

This finding is believed to be explained by the connection between adolescence and self-esteem as well as the variations in parenting styles among the households the people are raised in.

The study's subjects are all teenagers, ranging in age from 10 to 14. According to Rosenberg (1967) 33's analysis of the literature, people's self-esteem declines between the ages of 12 and 13, but it rises dramatically beyond 14 and into the early stages of adulthood. 34.

from youth to maturity, Baldwin and Hoffman (2002) came to the conclusion that reaching maturity and growing older are also beneficial, but that the degree of self-esteem throughout adolescence is more erratic. The study result is supported by this outcome.

In their research, Tiggeman and Williamson (2000) looked at the connection between exercise level and psychological well-being in 252 individuals ranging in age from 16 to 60. Taking into account one of the study's findings, exercise

It was discovered that there was a positive correlation for guys and a negative correlation for girls between self-esteem and doing. The study's outcome validates the research results.

McCarty and Hoge (1982) looked at how 37 teenagers' levels of self-esteem were affected by the age variable. One of the conclusions drawn from the study is that teenagers' levels of self-esteem rise in tandem with their ages.

According to Hatipoğlu (1996), the mean score on self-concept for male adolescents was greater than that of female adolescents in 38 secondary schools.

In their 39 research, Barnes and Farrier (1985) looked at pupils in the fifth and sixth grades. The study looked at the self-esteem scores of 583 teenagers. The study's findings led them to the conclusion that female adolescents had lower levels of self-esteem than male adolescents.

In his research, Dilek (2007, p. 62) 40 found that there is a connection between adolescent self-esteem growth and the parenting practices of the households in which people reside. According to him, traits like autonomous thought and decision-making—which are crucial for the growth

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of self-esteem—may suffer, particularly in those brought up in an authoritarian home environment.

Numerous elements are known to be useful in the development of self-esteem. The parents' educational attainment is one of these. Children's self-esteem rises in tandem with their parents' educational attainment 41. When taken into account in this context, it may be assumed that the study's sample of female teenagers from Istanbul's Sultanbeyli and Kartal districts was successful in excluding substantial differences.

Yegül (1999) observed no statistically significant difference in self-esteem measures between male teenagers ($n = 203$; ages 42–18) who participate in sports and those who do not.

Examining all of these data, it can be observed that there is no discernible difference between the average self-esteem ratings of females who play sports and those who do not, aged 10 to 14. Numerous factors are assumed to be involved, including the parents' educational attainment, the correlation between the age variable and girls' self-esteem growth, and the influence of their families' parenting practices. 213 female adolescents, ages 10 to 14, who were included in the research and either played sports or not had their levels of self-confidence evaluated. The findings showed that there was a statistically significant and positive correlation between the internal self-confidence ratings of female athletes and those of non-athletes. Thus, it may be concluded that participating in athletics improves people's internal self-confidence. This conclusion is corroborated by research found in the literature.

The self-confidence levels of 185 high school students who participated in 43 sports and those who did not were analyzed by Ekinçi et al. (2014). According to the study's findings, students who favor team sports have higher levels of internal self-confidence than students who don't play sports by a statistically significant margin.

Salar et al. (2012) 44 looked at a few different factors while examining the emotional states of athletes participating in both team and individual sports. The study's findings indicated that teenage athletes participating in team sports and solo sports had comparable levels of self-confidence.

Regular participation in sports offers several advantages, including boosting one's self-esteem and confidence, according to Zorba (2012, p. 21) 45. Can and Kaçar (2016) 46 looked at the connection between athletes' sense of self-worth and bravery vs how they saw their identities.

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The research, which included 176 players, found that bravery and inner confidence are favorably impacted by an athlete's impression of their sporting identity. After analyzing the external self-confidence scores of 213 female adolescents in the research, aged 10 to 14, it was found that participating in sports had a positive and substantial correlation with external self-confidence ratings. Teenagers who participate in sports are thus contrasted with those who do not in terms of their outward self-confidence ratings. This study showed that it was greater, therefore it can be concluded that doing athletics as a female teenager favorably affects adolescents' outward self-confidence.

, Can and Kaçar (2016) investigated the connection between the sense of self as an athlete and emotions of bravery and self-assurance. According to the study's findings, female athletes are more externally confident than their male counterparts.

of another research, the degrees of self-confidence of 179 high school athletes and inactive students were compared. It was determined from the data that those who participate in sports have better levels of internal and outward self-confidence than people who do not. A substantial and positive correlation was observed between the overall self-confidence score and the variable of participation in sports among the girls aged 10-14 who were part of the research. Thus, one of the things that contributes to secondary school girls' increased self-confidence is their participation in school sports teams.

In their study with 47 children in the sixth and seventh grades, Ryan and Dzewaltowski (2002) found that pupils who engaged in physical activities had higher levels of self-confidence.

Güneş and Eroğlu (2016) investigated the impact of licensed sports on self-confidence throughout 48 adolescence by studying 300 teenagers who participate in sports and those who do not. The results of the study indicate that teenagers who participate in sports have better levels of internal, external, and overall self-confidence than adolescents who do not participate in sports. This discovery validates the findings of our study.

In his research, Akıncı (2007) investigated the impact of physical education and sports on the process of socialization and personality development. The study involved 309 students who competed in sports between different branches of secondary education institutions in Isparta and were awarded the first three degrees. The study's findings showed that teenage athletes' involvement in sports enhanced their sense of confidence.

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